

In Silico Prediction on Antibacterial Phytochemicals of Flower of *Tagetes erecta* (Linn.) through Binding Pose and Interaction against Receptor (DNA Gyrase-B)

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ABSTRACT

An *in silico* prediction was evaluated the binding energy and molecular interaction for phytochemicals (flavonoids) of flower of marigold (*T. erecta* Linn.) against DNA gyrase B receptor (PDB ID: 3G7B). As per the class V phytochemicals namely Kaempferol, Kaempferol-3-O-glucoside, Kaempferitrin, Patuletin, and Patulitrin along with class IV synthetic antibiotic Ciprofloxacin were considered for molecular docking study. The virtual screening was conducted through PyRx docking tool. The findings revealed that the phytoligands Kaempferitrin (-7.6 Kcal/mol) and Patulitrin (-7.2) were obtained highly favourable than synthetic antibiotic viz. Ciprofloxacin (-6.4 Kcal/mol). Rests phytoligands were obtained lower binding energy. In conclusion, Kaempferitrin and Patulitrin could be an alternative for antibacterial lead small molecule(s) individually or combinations compared to synthetic drug. Moreover, it is suggested the functional bioassay with animal models and/or cell lines to authenticate this *in silico* study in future.

Keywords: Antibacterial drug, *In silico*, Molecular dynamics, Virtual screening, Phytoligands, *Tagetes erecta*

INTRODUCTION

Antibacterial medicines are essential for preventing a variety of bacterial infections, but there are potential side effects or resistance to harmful bacteria.[1,2] Researchers are focusing on utilizing plant-derived medications, known as phytomedicines, to limit the development of bacteria in order to avoid bacterial resistance. DNA gyrase enzyme, also known as type II topoisomerase,[3,4,5] is the most efficient of many bacterial enzymes for metabolic control and aids in the process of DNA replication. Phytoconstituents are well-established bioactive substances, which are easily extracted from natural sources, particularly plant products, known as “phytomedicines” that are used through traditional knowledge to prevent a variety of illnesses.[6-9] Regarding phytomedicines, produced by plants may be a good choice for natural products as anti-bacterial agents, which may use to prevent bacterial resistance[10] In this context, the selection of marigold flower (*Tagetes*

erecta Linn.) extract shows potential anti-bacterial properties as per experimental investigations by many researchers.[11-15] In the crude extract, some allelochemicals may pose toxicity,[16] in which *in silico* prediction especially molecular docking and interaction can easily identify the lead small molecule(s) as similar to synthetic antibiotics without side effects.[17-20] On the other hand, molecular dynamics (MD) simulation may help to detect the protein structural flexibility. The *de novo* peptide structure prediction can be done in which both cyclic and linear peptides and their conformational flexibility easily known.[21] Moreover, *in silico* prediction helps to save animals, cost and duration to identify lead small molecule(s) for new drug discovery.[22] This *in silico* prediction was to determine the binding energy and molecular interaction for phytochemicals (flavonoids) of *T. erecta* against the receptor call as “DNA gyrase B (PDB ID: 3G7B)”.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Selection of receptor

The receptor namely “DNA gyrase B (PDB ID: 3G7B)” was selected as per the earlier study by

Chakravarty et al. [19] A three-dimensional (3D) ribbon structure is depicted following visualization in MGL tool (Fig 1) developed by “The Scripps Research Institute”. [23]

Figure 1: 3D ribbon structure of DNA gyrase B [PDB ID: 3g7b; Chain A = Magenta colour attached with ligand (line structure) at 471 position and Chain B = white colour attached with ligand (line structure) at 472 position]

Selection of phyto and synthetic ligands

The phyto and synthetic ligands were selected as per our previous study on toxicity prediction by Dalal and Talapatra. [24] As per the class V phytocompounds namely “Kaempferol, Kaempferol-3-O-glucoside, Kaempferitrin, Patuletin, and Patulitrin” along with class IV synthetic antibiotic viz. Ciprofloxacin were considered for molecular docking study. 3D structure of each ligand is depicted in Fig 2.

Study of molecular docking and interaction

The molecular docking and interaction to determine binding energy and amino acids interaction was carried out by using a tool namely PyRx (Version, 0.8) built by Trott and Olson, [25] which was used in an earlier study. [19] Docking of 5 phytocompounds (flavonoids) and 1 antibiotic namely ciprofloxacin as ligands against above-mentioned receptor (PDB ID: 3G7B) were analysed. To identify the residues involved in each case of receptor-ligand interaction to detect antibacterial property. The 3-D grid box size values and central position values were elaborated in earlier study. [19]

Figure 2: Three-dimensional structure of phytochemicals (A = Kaempferol; B = Kaempferol-3-O-glucoside; C = Kaempferitrin; D = Patuletin; E = Patulitrin;) and synthetic medicine (F = Ciprofloxacin)

Study of molecular dynamics of receptor

The molecular dynamics (MD) simulation for above-mentioned receptor (PDB IDs: 3G7B) was separately simulated by using CABS flex (version, 3.0) online server as per the method developed by Kuriata et al.[26] Moreover, unique CABS-flex server was explored in depth to a different place.[27] All-atom MD data were used to validate the findings of the CABS-flex modelling and experimental structures as per Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy.[28,29] The technique was also thoroughly evaluated as a module of modelling methods for predicting protein solubility[30] and flexible peptide docking.[26,31-33]

RESULTS

Table 1 reveals the binding energy values in which the phytoligands Kaempferitrin (-7.6 Kcal/mol) and

Patulitrin (-7.2) were obtained highly favourable when compared to synthetic antibiotic viz. Ciprofloxacin (-6.4 Kcal/mol). Rests phytoligands were obtained lower binding energy. Regarding contact residue and hydrogen bonding, Kaempferitrin obtained amino acid residues viz. TRP49, Val48, Glu50, ILE51, Val52 with 1 hydrogen bond, Asn54 with 1 hydrogen bond, Asp53 with 1 hydrogen bond, Ile51, Ser55, Ile56, Asp57 in Chain B with 1 unknown hydrogen bond (Fig 2). For Patulitrin, some similar contact residues viz. TRP49, Glu50, ILE51, Val52, Asn54, Asp53, Ser55, Ile56, Asp57 in Chain B with 1 unknown hydrogen bond in Chain B were obtained (Fig 3). Rests Fig 4, 5 and 6 similar amino acid residues were obtained in chain B. For Ciprofloxacin, similar contact residues viz. Trp49, Glu50, Val52, Asp53, Ile51, ASN54, Ser55, Asp57 were also obtained in Chain B without hydrogen bonding (Fig 8).

Table 1: Energy values and contact residues as per receptor-ligand binding

Ligands	Binding energy (Kcal/mol)	Contact residue and hydrogen bonding
Phytochemicals		

Kaempferitrin	-7.6	TRP49, Val48, Glu50, ILE51, Val52 with 1 hydrogen bond, Asn54 with 1 hydrogen bond, Asp53 with 1 hydrogen bond, Ile51, Ser55, Ile56, Asp57 in Chain B with 1 unknown hydrogen bond
Patulitrin	-7.2	TRP49, Glu50, ILE51, Val52, Asn54, Asp53, Ser55, Ile56, Asp57 in Chain B with 1 unknown hydrogen bond
Patuletin	-6.8	Glu50, Ile51, Asn54, Asp53, Asp57 in Chain B
Kaempferol-3-O-glucoside	-6.6	Trp49, Glu50, Asp53, Asp57, ASN54 in Chain B with 1 unknown hydrogen bond
Kaempferol	-6.4	Asp57, Asp53, Val52, ASN54, Ile51, Glu50 in Chain B
Synthetic antibiotic		
Ciprofloxacin	-6.4	Trp49, Glu50, Val52, Asp53, Ile51, ASN54, Ser55, Asp57 in Chain B

Fig 9 highlighted 3D structures as per 10 final models, which obtained the structure data of target protein as DNA gyrase B (PDB ID: 3G7B). As per the tool, an interactive molecular viewer obtained the visual analysis in which the structural heterogeneity indicated.

Fig 10 exhibited the “Contact maps” tab that obtained a complete vision of the residue-residue interaction patterns of target protein. The panel centrally shown a communicating contact map between residues. In this map, each dot symbolized an interaction through a pair of residues.

Figure 3: Pose and interaction of Kaempferitrin

Figure4: Pose and interaction of Patulitrin

Figure5: Pose and interaction of Patuletin

Figure 6: Pose and interaction of Kaempferol-3-O-glucoside

Figure 7: Pose and interaction of Kaempferol

Figure 8: Pose and interaction of Ciprofloxacin

Its colour was determined by how often this specific interaction occurred within the models set utilized to produce data for this map. Moreover, the contact maps produced a matrix along with connections within the

colour scale shown right side (at the contact between residue 24-230 in chain A and 24-227 in chain B, an information balloon with contact information appeared)for the studied protein.

Figure9: Ribbon structure of all models for DNA gyrase B (PDB ID: 3G7B)

Figure10: Contact maps for chain A and B separately shows a matrix with contacts with the colour scale

In Fig 11, the “Fluctuation plot” tab key provided an interactive 2D plot representing residue-wise fluctuations noted throughout the simulation. The calculations for the fluctuations were obtained as root

mean square fluctuation (RMSF) after global superposition. For chain A, MD simulation predicted the highest RMSF value was of about 3.941 Å while for chain B, MD simulation predicted the highest RMSF value was of about 3.623 Å.

Figure11: ‘Fluctuation plots’ for chain A and B separately shows the residue fluctuation profile as RMSF for studied protein

DISCUSSION

In the present *in silico* study, phytolignans Kaempferitrin and Patulitrin were obtained highly favourable binding energy in comparison with Ciprofloxacin. While Kaempferol obtained similar

binding energy like Ciprofloxacin. All the contact residues were similar for these above-mentioned phytolignans. Recent *in silico* study by Majumdar and Mandal reported that Kaempferol and its derivatives have potent antibacterial properties [34]. Interestingly, Rhama and Madhavan experimented

with isolated flavonoid from the flower of *Tagetes erecta* Linn. in which Patulitrin recognized antibacterial potentials against several bacteria [35]. Virtual screening in which an early set of ligands expected for binding a target, is another possible use for MD. Docking programs are used in conventional virtual screening utilizing a definite structure of the target protein [36]. In fact, the pocket within binding site could be quite flexible, and as a result, only a subset of binders will be found by docking to a single structure. Several potential structures discovered by simulation might enhance the variety of binding ligands found [37-39]. It was reported that the fluctuation should be within the Rg value between 0.0 to 0.4 nm which is within the acceptable range of 3.4 Å [40] and similar findings observed by Kumar et al. in which the Rg values were between the range of 1.63-1.73 nm along with maximum clustering between 1.65-1.70 nm for AM1- and AM5-DNA gyrase complex [41]. But in this study, exceeded the acceptable range.

CONCLUSION

These two phytoligands viz. Kaempferitrin and Patulitrin could be an alternative for antibacterial lead small molecule(s) individually or combinations compared to synthetic drug. Moreover, it is suggested the functional bioassay to validate this *in silico* study in near future.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

Authors declare no conflict of interest in this study.

ABBREVIATIONS

DNA – Deoxy ribonucleic acid

Linn. – Linnaeus

MD – Molecular dynamics

MGL – Molecular graphics laboratory

PDB – Protein data bank

RMSF – Root mean square fluctuation

3D – Three dimensional

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